

Dibenzophenazine based TADF emitters as dual electrochromic and electroluminescence materials

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Abstract: Previous works reported the synthesis of donor-acceptor-donor molecules based on dibenzophenazine acceptor group, presenting thermally activated delayed fluorescent (TADF) properties and their application in the assembly of highly efficient electroluminescent devices. Herein, we focus on the characterisation of charge carrier species through UV-Vis-NIR spectroelectrochemical and potentiostatic EPR techniques, in addition to the investigation of electropolymerisation properties of some compounds depicted in this study. The promising electrochromic features of both small molecules and conjugated polymers led to the assembly and investigation of electrochromic devices, evidencing the materials' versatility, applied in such different approaches as electrochromic windows and electroluminescent devices. Furthermore, the assembled OLEDs provided high efficiencies, with small roll-off, EQEs up to 20.5% and luminance values up to 85 000 cd/m².

Introduction

Optoelectronic systems become intrinsic to our everyday lives, and as a consequence, we must find a way to develop more efficient devices which are able to provide high performance with reduced waste of energy.^[1–3] Organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs) are promising for producing brighter and more efficient displays within thinner, lighter and even curved devices.^[4–7] For a couple of years, there has been an approach to developing transparent OLED devices where the screen is deposited on electrochromic windows. We can have a transparent structure or TV in our mirror, cabinet, or fridge if needed. If we look at the OLED emitter structures, they are conjugated molecules possessing chromophoric donor and acceptor groups.^[8,9] In many cases, such molecules should also have electrochromic properties.^[10,11] So instead of developing new organic compounds, it's worth investigating existing ones for multapplicable properties.^[12,13] A perfect example is a PEDOT:PSS, a material that is used in most organic electronic devices like OLEDs, OPVs, OFETs, OTGs and electrochromic windows.^[14]

The biggest inconvenience of using OLEDs is their limitation of 25% of internal quantum efficiency (IQE) when pure fluorescent emitters are applied, which bounds the external quantum

efficiency (EQE) of this type of device.^[15–17] Molecular structures containing donor and acceptor moieties conveniently spatially organised can achieve truly small gaps between energies of triplet and singlet excited states (ΔE_{ST}).^[18,19] For gaps small enough, only the increase of molecular vibration by the thermal energy from the surrounding media is required as the activation energy for the hybridisation process between excited states, allowing up to 100% of IQE, producing what is known as thermally activated delayed fluorescence (TADF) emission.^[17,20]

Several emitters with donor-acceptor-donor (D-A-D) flexible structures based on dibenzophenazine acceptor unit were previously synthesised and reported along with their structural photophysical characterisation. A complete study of TADF emission properties was carried out in addition to the application of such emitters in the fabrication of OLED devices, reaching high EQE values (up to 16.8%) as well as mechanochromic luminescent properties in some of the analysed compounds.^[12,14] Due to their small values of ΔE_{ST} , high EQEs and the possibility of varying colour emission from applied mechanical forces, these materials were chosen for a more detailed investigation in an attempt to accomplish a better understanding of the influence of the effect of different donors in their spectral properties. The emitters investigated in this study are presented in Figure 1, where nearly all the molecules were previously reported in limited study,^[19,21] with the exception of compound **5**, which was included here to allow a more comprehensive comparative overview. The most interesting feature of this family of emitters is that compounds **3**, **5** and **7** exhibits the ability to undergo polymerisation reactions promoted by electrochemical conditions, which was failed to be mentioned in previous reports.

In this work, polymer formation was investigated through cyclic voltammetry as well as the determination of electrochemical bandgap and energies of the highest occupied molecular orbitals (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) for monomers and resulted polymers. The spectroelectrochemical investigation resulting from the combination of electrochemical with any spectral technique allows to detect of the formation of charge carrier species,^[22,23] and in this way, helps to identify side reactions that may occur during the voltage applied to the emitter

RESEARCH ARTICLE

layer,^[24] especially the production of by-products that may impair device efficiency.^[25]

Figure 1. Chemical structures of dibenzophenazine-based emitters.

These techniques make it possible to track spectral changes regarding the formation of polarons (and bipolarons), which consist of charged species produced under electrochemical conditions.^[26–28] Herein, we present the full spectroelectrochemical study of dibenzophenazine-based emitters (Figure 1) and their polymerised products by combining UV-Vis-NIR and EPR with electrochemical analysis.

Moreover, materials are characterised by the variation of colour emission or transparency towards the light, arising from interaction with an applied electric field.^[29,30] In cases where the colour variation is confined in the visible range of spectra, such materials can be applied in the manufacture of optoelectronic devices.^[31] Organic polymeric materials exhibiting electrochromic properties are highly interesting for producing devices with stable films, achieving high colour contrast, high conductivity, fast switching and low cost of production.^[32,33] Electrochromic devices containing compounds **1–8** (Figure 1) and polymers **P3**, **P5** and **P7** were assembled and characterised as a way of taking advantage of the unique contrast of spectral characteristics of such materials to produce efficient optoelectronic devices. TADF-based OLEDs were also fabricated, and their properties were determined to support the comparison of electroluminescent behaviour of novel compound **5** with its analogous emitters.

This work aims to better understand and characterise the formation of charge carrier species of this group of TADF emitters, granting opportunities for developing more efficient devices containing organic functional materials in the future.

Results and Discussion

Electrochemical analysis. As the first step of the investigation of this set of compounds, oxidation and reduction processes were determined through cyclic voltammetry measurements. Compounds **1–8** were analysed from -2 to 2 V, which is the potential window established for the setup of DCM and

Bu_4NBF_4 ,^[34] yet only the electroactive processes are depicted in Figure 2 to ensure clearer observation. In electrochemical studies, when the potential applied reaches the maximum selected potential boundary, it is usually known as the doping step. The process of returning to the initial potential value (at the beginning of the measurement) can be called the dedoping stage. The first noticeable behaviour is that all compounds share a similar individual reduction peak close to -2 V vs Fc/Fc^+ , regarding reducing the dibenzophenazine acceptor group. Compounds **1**, **2**, **4**, **6** and **8** present similar behaviour, first reversible oxidation, followed by a second (or a third) semi-reversible or irreversible oxidation peaks. Compounds **3**, **5** and **7** display the highest potentials for first oxidation processes. More than that, compounds **3** and **7** (black lines in Figure 2b,d) display unique behaviour during dedoping of the oxidation process, one of two peaks presents sharp and high current characteristics. The distinct behaviour of such compounds is the first evidence of their ability to undergo polymerisation under an electrochemical environment.

Figure 2. Cyclic voltammograms of 1 mM of compounds a) **1** and **2**, b) **3** and **4**, c) **5** and **6**, d) **7** and **8** in DCM containing 0.1 M Bu_4NBF_4 as electrolyte. Pt disk working, Pt wire as counter and Ag/AgCl as reference electrodes, at 50 mV s^{-1} scan rate.

During the doping stage of oxidation, only a monomer is present in the analysed solution, therefore, the voltammetric signal refers only to the monomer. If the potential chosen provides enough energy, the electropolymerisation reaction occurs, leaving evidence during the dedoping process. Hence, during the first oxidation scan, voltammograms of electropolymerisation of compounds **3**, **5** and **7** (Figure 3) exhibit monomer's oxidation peaks, while new oxidation peaks are noticed in second and further scans at lower potential values regarding the polymeric materials being formed. The lower potentials indicate that such products exhibit higher conjugation length than the initial monomer, and the constant increase of current between consecutive scans indicates the successful electrodeposition of the materials onto the electrode's surface. Through cyclic voltammetric measurements of electropolymerisation reaction

using different potential boundaries, starting polymerisation potentials were determined as 0.72, 0.98 and 0.83 V for **P3**, **P5** and **P7**, respectively.

Figure 3. Cyclic voltammograms for the electropolymerisation (black line) of 1 mM solutions of compounds a) **3**, b) **5**, and c) **7**; and for the oxidation of the polymeric films (red line) formed in the electrode surface. Measurements were carried out in 0.1 M Bu₄NBF₄ solution in DCM at a 50 mV s⁻¹ scan rate.

Analysing the voltammograms of compounds **3**, **5** and **7** (Figure 2b,c,d), it can be noticed that the first steps of oxidation processes are very subtle, like a “shoulder” of the following oxidation step and the starting polymerisation potentials are placed at the end of the second stage of monomer’s oxidation.

Afterwards, the electrodes are rinsed thoroughly and immersed in an electrolyte solution to analyse the electrochemical stability of polymers, depicted (in red) in Figure 3 and Figure S1 in the Supporting Information, regarding the voltammetric responses of pure polymers. It is important to mention that the lowest potential signal in the red line in Figure 3b is only noticed at the first scan, not appearing in all following scans (2-10), therefore, it is characterised as a charge trapping phenomenon and is not related to the polymer’s oxidation.

As a consequence of the electrochemical investigation, through the employment of onset potential values of first oxidation and first reduction processes, it can be determined HOMO and LUMO energy levels, along with electrochemical bandgap for monomers and polymers, as displayed in Figure 4.

Figure 4. HOMO and LUMO energy levels and electrochemical bandgap values for compounds **1** – **8**, determined by cyclic voltammetry.

Since all compounds share the same acceptor unit, dibenzophenazine group, values regarding LUMO levels are similar, varying from -3.17 and -3.41 eV. The smallest bandgaps were attributed to compounds **2** and **6**. Compounds **1** and **8** exhibit very similar HOMO and LUMO levels, presenting similar molecular structures containing phenothiazine and phenoxazine donor groups. Comparing the electrochemical bandgaps between monomers and polymers, all the polymers have higher HOMO

energy levels and smaller bandgaps, which is associated with higher conjugation lengths.

UV-Vis-NIR spectroelectrochemical analysis. The combination of UV-Vis absorbance spectroscopy and electrochemistry allows the characterisation of charge carrier species. At initial potential increase, the first observed spectral changes are attributed as polaron bands, singly charged species. With the continuing potential increase, polaron bands start to decrease. It is observable the appearance of other bands at lower wavelength represent the second stage of oxidation while forming bipolarons (double-charged species).

Compounds **1**, **2**, **4**, **6** and **8**, which do not exhibit electropolymerisation properties, were investigated through spectroelectrochemical UV-Vis and NIR measurements and their spectra are depicted in Figure S2. The spectral changes during the first electrochemical scans of compound **1** are barely noticeable, only in the fifth (and last) cycle, a slight increase in the band at 551 nm, can be observed during the dedoping in Figure S2b. The formation of bipolaronic species directly from polarons of compound **2** (Figures S2c and S2d) is indicated by the presence of an isosbestic point. In the case of Compounds **4** and **8**, we observe new absorbance bands appearing and rising during doping (Figures S2e and S2i). Compound **3** displays a unique behaviour during spectroelectrochemical analysis. As shown in Figure 5a, two broad signals appear and rise on doping process, which decreases during dedoping (Figure 5b) until the disappearance of one of the signals (780 nm), however, a very defined signal (618 nm) stays stable during all successive potential cycles (scans). Through the cyclovoltabsorptometric analysis in Figure 5, it could be easily noticed the signal around 1425 nm appear only at the dedoping stage, just after the disappearance of the signal at 780 nm. The development of a stable signal at 618 nm is evidence for the electropolymerisation reaction. In this case, any observed spectral change is associated with monomer’s and polymer’s charge carriers. Afterwards, the ITO electrode containing the electrodeposited polymer **P3** was rinsed and placed into an electrolyte solution for the spectroelectrochemical analysis of the pure polymeric film, spectra of doping, and dedoping processes are shown in Figure 5c and 5d, respectively. Several spectra changes are noticed for polymer **P3**. Yet, the most distinguishable are the bands at 762 nm and 1491 nm, which can be tracked by the cyclovoltabsorptometric analysis in Figure 5f, being characterised with bipolaronic and polaronic features, respectively.

Figure 5. Potentiodynamic UV-Vis-NIR spectroelectrochemical analysis of doping process of a) 0.25 mM of compound **3** and c) polymer **P3**; dedoping process of b) 0.25 mM of compound **3** and d) polymer **P3** in DCM Bu₄NBF₄ (0.1 M) electrolyte. Cyclovoltabsorptometric measurement of e) electropolymerisation of **3** and f) electrochemical stability of the polymer **P3**. With ITO working, Pt wire as counter and Ag/AgCl as reference electrodes, at 50 mv s⁻¹ scan rate.

Spectroelectrochemical analysis of compound **5** is presented in Figure 6. Tracking the processes shown in Figure 6e, it can be noticed on the end of the doping step (Figure 6a), the appearance of a signal around 760 nm, which disappears during the dedoping stage (Figure 6b), giving place to a signal at 541 nm that stays stable until the end of the cycle. Unfortunately, the low solubility of compound **5** is assumed to be the cause of poor film deposition, causing low-quality UV-Vis and NIR spectroelectrochemical spectra of polymer **P5** (Figure 6c and 6d). Still, it is possible to detect the activity in the NIR region through the electrochemical scan, confirming polaronic features, easily tracked by the cyclovoltabsorptometric plot in Figure 6f.

Figure 6. Potentiodynamic UV-Vis-NIR spectroelectrochemical analysis of doping process of a) 0.25 mM of compound **5** and c) polymer **P5**; dedoping process of b) 0.25 mM of compound **3** and d) polymer **P5** in DCM Bu₄NBF₄ (0.1 M) electrolyte. Cyclovoltabsorptometric measurement of e) electropolymerisation of **5** and f) electrochemical stability of the polymer **P5**. With ITO working, Pt wire as counter and Ag/AgCl as reference electrodes, at 50 mv s⁻¹ scan rate.

The spectroelectrochemical behaviour of compound **7** and polymer **P7** are displayed in Figure 7. As with any other electropolymerisation process, the spectral changes cannot be separated for the pure monomer, and as can be seen in Figure 7, the spectral behaviour of monomers and polymer's charge carriers are quite similar. The main difference is that during the first doping step (Figure 7a), there is no polymer formed yet, therefore, is not seen any spectral activity in the higher NIR region (higher than 1000 nm). By means of tracking the cyclovoltabsorptometric plot in Figure 7e, it can be noticed that a signal at 1560 nm is formed only during the dedoping stage (Figure 7b). Charge carriers' spectral behaviour of polymer **P7** are quite distinct than its neutral species, however, the most interesting features are the emergence of multiple signals with maxima at 795 and 1590 nm during doping (Figure 7c) and dedoping (Figure 7d) processes. Observing the cyclovoltabsorptometric analysis in Figure 7f, the bands at 795 and 1590 nm are characterised as bipolaronic and polaronic, respectively.

Figure 7. Potentiodynamic UV-Vis-NIR spectroelectrochemical analysis of doping process of a) 0.25 mM of compound **7** and c) polymer **P7**; dedoping process of b) 0.25 mM of compound **7** and d) polymer **P7** in DCM Bu₄NBF₄ (0.1 M) electrolyte. Cyclovoltabsorptometric measurement of e) electropolymerisation of **7** and f) electrochemical stability of the polymer **P7**. With ITO working, Pt wire as counter and Ag/AgCl as reference electrodes, at 50 mV s⁻¹ scan rate.

The main difference between compounds that undergo electropolymerisation and those that don't is the spectral activity in NIR regions. More specifically, compounds **1**, **2**, **4**, **6** and **8** present no spectral changes during the electrochemical measurements, while compounds **3** and **7** exhibits the emergence of signals around 1500 nm, related to the polaronic species.

As well as voltammetric techniques, UV-Vis absorbance spectra can also gather information about the difference between HOMO and LUMO energy levels. Table 1 displays bandgaps acquired from cyclic voltammetry and UV-Vis spectroscopic techniques, called electrochemical and optical bandgap, respectively.

Table 1. Comparison between electrochemical and optical bandgaps of monomers and polymers.

Compound	Electrochemical bandgap (eV)	Optical bandgap (eV)
3	2.29	2.35
P3	2.18	2.20
5	2.19	2.62
P5	2.11	2.44
7	2.19	2.48
P7	1.99	2.36

Compound **3** and polymer **P3** present very similar values for the two types of bandgap determination. Even though they are called similarly, the electrochemical bandgap is associated with the

energy required for the ionisation process, while optical bandgap is related to the energy difference between ground and excited states generated through photoexcitation is not possible to make a straightforward comparison.^[35]

Potentiostatic EPR. Compounds **1-8** were analysed through the combination of EPR and voltammetric techniques as a way to complement the spectroelectrochemical studies. Potentiostatic EPR spectra during the doping stage of oxidation processes are presented in Figure S3 in Supporting Information. EPR signal for compound **1** (Figure S2a) undergoes a rapid growth after 0.6 V until 1.2 V when it starts to decrease. The sudden intensity drop is attributed to the formation of bipolaronic species at the second stage of the oxidation process that occurs around 1.0 V (Figure 2a). Compound **2** (Figure S2b) exhibits similar behaviour, with the appearance of a signal at 0.2 V followed by intense growth and at potentials higher than 0.8 V, the signal decreased its intensity, representing the formation of bipolarons, potential values coincide with first and second oxidation steps, which initiate at 0.13 and 0.8 V (Figure 2a). Compounds **3-8** present a continuous growth of signal intensity up until the end of the doping stage (Figures S2c-h). The more significant difference among potentiostatic EPR spectra is the presence or absence of hyperfine splitting. Compounds **3**, **5** and **7** (Figures S2c,e,g) have no hyperfine splitting pattern, representing that the formed charged is located in carbon atoms. While compounds **1**, **2**, **4**, **6** and **8** display diverse shapes of hyperfine splitting, indicating that the charge in radical species is located in different atoms, in this case looking like triple hyperfine splitting regarding nitrogen atoms.

Electropolymerizable compounds **3**, **5** and **7** exhibit broad low-intense signals at the beginning of the doping stage, especially compounds **3** and **7** (Figure 8a,g). Yet, at the dedoping process (Figures 8b,e,h), the EPR signals become sharp and high intensity. These sharp signals are related to polymer deposition on the electrode's surface, which can only be observed at the end of the oxidation process (doping) or the inverse reduction (dedoping) step. For example, during the doping process of compound **3** (Figure 8a), a broad signal at 0.9 V is noticed, which rises to turn into a strong, intense signal at the dedoping stage (Figure 8b), continuing to increase until the end of the analysis. Likewise, compound **7** (Figure 8g) presents the emergence of a broad signal that becomes sharp and intense during dedoping (Figure 8h), only in this case, decreases its intensity at the end, although not losing its sharp shape. On the other hand, doping of compound **5** (Figure 8d) exhibits the appearance of an EPR signal at 0.9 V, which continues to increase in intensity at the start of the dedoping stage (Figure 8e) until 0.7V, when it undergoes a sudden decrease until its disappearance at 0.2 V.

After analysing electropolymerisation of compounds **3**, **5** and **7**, the working electrode was rinsed and placed in a cell containing electrolyte solution for the potentiostatic EPR analysis of pure polymeric films. The doping process of polymer **P3** (Figure 8c) exhibits the appearance of a signal at 0.4 V, which undergoes a sudden increase until 0.6 V, followed by a decrease and disappearance at 0.9 V related to the formation of bipolaronic species, confirmed by cyclic voltammetric measurements of **P3** (Figure 3a). In the same way, polymers **P5** and **P7** present two stages of the oxidation process (Figure 3b,c), hence, both cases display the emergence of signal (at 0.6 and 0.4 V) followed by a decrease and signal disappearance (Figure 8f, i). Bipolaronic

double-charged charge carriers, in this case, are forming non-paramagnetic species.

Figure 8. Potentiostatic EPR spectroelectrochemistry of oxidation during doping process of a) 0.5 mM of compound **3**, c) polymer **P3**, d) 0.5 mM of compound **5**, f) polymer **P5**, g) 0.5 mM of compound **7**, and i) polymer **P7**; dedoping process of b) 0.5 mM of compound **3**, e) 0.5 mM of compound **5** and h) 0.5 mM of compound **7**. Pt wire working, Pt wire as counter and Ag/AgCl as reference electrodes, at 50 mV s⁻¹ scan rate.

Compounds **3** and **5** share similar structures with non-polymerisable compounds **4** and **6**. The main difference is the addition of alkyl substituents in similar electronic positions of compounds **4** and **6**, which impedes the formation of radical on the carbon atom, necessary for the electropolymerisation reaction. Potentiostatic EPR spectra were acquired during the reduction of compounds **1-8**. However, not all compounds generated detectable responses by EPR technique, spectra of reduction of compounds **1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 8** and polymer **P3** are presented in Figure S4b-h in Supporting Information. As the reduction process is associated with the electron affinity of the molecule, and all compounds share the same acceptor unit, pure dibenzophenazine was also analysed by potentiostatic EPR (Figure S4a). Compounds **1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7** and dibenzophenazine exhibit emergence of signal, followed by continuous gradual rise until maximum potential. Compounds **5** and **7** (Figure S4e,g) share a similar signal shape with pure dibenzophenazine acceptor (Figure S4a). Near all acquired spectra display hyperfine coupling, indicating the charge position over different nitrogen atoms. The only compound which did not present hyperfine coupling during reduction was polymer **P3** (Figure S4h).

Electrochromic properties. Electrochromic layers were manufactured with compounds **1-8** and polymers **P3, P5** and **P7**. The electrochromic properties are summarised in Table 2. The best colour efficiencies (CE) results were attributed to compounds **2, 8, P3** and **P7**, with obtained values over 300 cm² C⁻¹. Such high values of CE are very promising for future structural optimisation.

Table 2. Electrochromic properties of investigated compounds. λ – investigated wavelength; T_{ox} – transmittance of oxidised film at given wavelength λ ; T_{red} – transmittance of neutral film at given wavelength λ ; ΔOD – a difference of optical density between neutral and oxidised film at given wavelength λ ; QD – charge density calculated in a chronocoulometric experiment; CE – colouration efficiency; CR – contrast ratio. For further information, please see previous works.

Compound	λ (nm)	T_{red} (%)	T_{ox} (%)	ΔOD	QD (mC cm ²)	CE (cm ² C ⁻¹)	CR (-)
1	551	99.31	77.62	0.107	0.83	128.28	1.28
2	578	98.86	28.84	0.535	1.26	423.97	3.43
3	621	99.54	52.48	0.278	1.45	191.29	1.90
4	781	98.86	67.61	0.165	1.37	120.73	1.46
5	768	97.95	60.26	0.211	1.07	197.75	1.63
6	559	99.54	58.88	0.228	1.76	129.60	1.69
7	804	99.77	22.39	0.649	3.72	174.33	4.46
8	532	99.31	33.11	0.477	1.44	330.15	3.00
P3	679	99.54	35.48	0.448	0.96	466.47	2.81
P5	1183	99.77	67.61	0.169	5.53	30.57	1.48
P7	787	95.50	15.14	0.800	1.79	446.68	6.31

The absorptivity in the NIR region is the most significant difference among compounds that exhibit the ability of electropolymerisation and the ones that don't. Intending to produce electrochromic devices active in the NIR region, the most interesting device contains polymer **P5**, which displayed absorption at the highest wavelength (1183 nm), however, such device achieved a relatively small CE value (30.57 cm² C⁻¹), which is inadequate for the assembly of efficient devices. Unfortunately, the characterisation did not result in the desired parameters for the application of such devices. However, structural optimisation may present improved properties. The polymeric films used for electrochromic devices containing **P3, P5** and **P7** were deposited by electropolymerisation, which usually results in very low uniformity layers. Perhaps, using more sophisticated solution process methods may result in devices with improved efficiencies.

Electroluminescent devices. Due to the novelty of compound **5**, electroluminescent devices were assembled for characterisation purposes, along with a proper comparison of the photophysical properties of compound **5** with its analogous structures. Hence, TADF-based OLED devices were fabricated using compounds **1-8** as emitter layers of improved device structures compared to previously reported results. A device structure containing ITO | HAT-CN(10 nm) | NPB(30 nm) | CBP co 10% **1-8** (30 nm) | TPBi (50 nm) | LiF (0.8nm) | Al(100 nm) (Dev 1-8) was used for the characterisation of electroluminescent properties of emitters, and their device characterisation is depicted in Figure 9.

Electroluminescence emission (Figure 9a) was observed in a wide range of wavelengths, with emission maxima varying from 494 nm (Dev5) to 642 nm (Dev2). All devices exhibited very small roll-off, which can be observed by the slight decrease in efficiency with increased current density in Figure 9c. Compounds **1, 2, 4, 7** and **8** improved their EQEs and luminance values compared to

RESEARCH ARTICLE

previous reports.^[19,21] The highest efficiency was found for Dev8 (EQE 20.5%), based on phenoxazine donor, while the lowest efficiency was observed for Dev6 (EQE 7.5%), containing *tert*-butylcarbazole derivative as an emitter. Device-based on compound **8** also exhibit the highest OLED luminance values, up to 85 000 cd/m², followed by Dev1, containing phenothiazine, with the second-highest luminance, up to 77 000 cd/m². Improved device structure resulted in higher efficiency and stability for all the previously reported compounds.^[19,21] Apparently, the electropolymerisation ability of compounds **3**, **5** and **7** are not leading to device degradation.

An interesting comparison can be made between compounds **5** and **6**, containing carbazole and *tert*-butylcarbazole. In Figure 9c, a significant increase in the OLED efficiency for compound **5**, with the absence of the alkyl group, presenting 14.5% EQE. This increase can be attributed to removing the TTA process, observed for emitter **6** in the previous report.^[21] The existence of the TTA process limits the emission efficiency, whereas its removal could influence the TADF behaviour.

Figure 9. OLED device characteristics: a) electroluminescence spectra; b) current density vs. voltage characteristics; c) EQE vs. current density; b) luminance vs. current density;

Conclusion

A group of TADF D-A-D dibenzphenazine electroactive derivatives was presented along with their electrochemical, spectroelectrochemical, electrochromic and electroluminescent properties. By combining results from these different techniques, molecular structures were proposed for the products of electropolymerisation reactions. A comparative study among materials that exhibit the ability to be electropolymerised and those that don't display the main spectral differences during employment of electrochemical conditions. Furthermore, our analysis considered the possibility of multiusage of TADF emitters, not limited to OLEDs but also as electrochromic materials.

Nevertheless, there are disadvantages to using small molecules as an electrochromic layer, such as the use of very polar solvents or the need to impregnate the emitters directly in the gel electrolyte. A novel compound **5** is reported to complete a family of diphenylphenazine D-A-D compounds, together with the assembly of OLED devices with improved structure, resulting in enhanced EQE and luminance as to previous reports.

Experimental Section

General synthesis. Unless otherwise noted, all reactions were carried out under an atmosphere of nitrogen gas. Melting points were determined on a Stanford Research Systems MPA100 OptiMelt Automated Melting Point System. ¹H and ¹³C spectra were recorded on a JEOL JMT-C400/54/SS Spectrometer (¹H NMR, 400 MHz; ¹³C NMR, 100 MHz) using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard ($\delta = 0$ ppm). Infrared spectra were acquired on a SHIMADZU IRAffinity-1 FT-IR Spectrometer. Mass spectra and High-resolution mass spectra were obtained on a JEOL JMS-700 Mass Spectrometer. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed with TG/DTA-7200 system (SII Nano Technology Inc.). Products were purified by chromatography on silica gel BW-300 and Chromatorex NH (Fuji Silysia Chemical Ltd.). Analytical thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on pre-coated silica gel glass plates (Merck silica gel 60 F254 and Fuji Silysia Chromatorex NH, 0.25 mm thickness). Compounds were visualised with a UV lamp. The compounds **1–4** and **6–8** were prepared according to the procedures described in our earlier work.^[19,21] The synthetic procedure for new compound **5** and its characterisation data are disclosed in the Supporting Information.

Materials. Electrochemical studies were conducted in 0.1 M solutions of tetrabutylammonium tetrafluoroborate (Bu₄NBF₄), 99% (Sigma–Aldrich) in dichloromethane (DCM) solvent, CHROMASOLV®, 99.9% (Sigma Aldrich) at room temperature. UV–vis spectroelectrochemical measurements were performed on ITO (Indium Tin Oxide) quartz glass working electrode. For polymers' analysis the ITO was coated with the polymers. Polymeric layers were synthesized on an ITO and Platinum (Pt) wire electrodes in similar conditions to cyclic voltammetric measurements. The investigated dibenzophenazine compounds, 3,11-Di(10*H*-phenothiazin-10-yl)dibenzo[*a,j*]phenazine (**1**), 3,11-Bis(3,7-di-*tert*-butyl-10*H*-phenothiazin-10-yl)dibenzo[*a,j*]phenazine (**2**), 3,11-Bis(diphenylamino)dibenzo[*a,j*]phenazine (**3**), 3,11-Bis[*N,N*-di(4-methoxyphenyl)amino]dibenzo[*a,j*]phenazine (**4**), 3,11-bis(3,6-di-*tert*-butyl-9*H*-carbazol-9-yl)dibenzo[*a,j*]phenazine (**6**), 3,11-bis(9,9-dimethylacridin-10(9*H*)-yl)dibenzo[*a,j*]phenazine (**7**) and 3,11-di(10*H*-phenoxazin-10-yl)dibenzo[*a,j*]phenazine (**8**) were previously synthesized as previously described.^[12,14] The synthetic procedure for 3,11-di(9*H*-carbazol-9-yl)dibenzo[*a,j*]phenazine (**5**) is described in the SI.

Electrochemistry and spectroelectrochemistry. The electrochemical investigation was carried out using potentiostats Autolab PGSTAT20 and Biologic SP150 system. Cyclic voltammetric measurements were conducted with 1 mM emitters' solutions (with exception of compound **5** = 0.5 mM) with 0.1 M BF₄ in DCM, at room temperature and 50 mV/s potential rate, calibrated against ferrocene/ferrocenium (Fc/Fc⁺) redox couple. The electrochemical cell comprised a 1 mm diameter platinum (Pt) disk as working electrode (WE), Ag/AgCl electrode as reference electrode (RE) and platinum coil as an auxiliary electrode (AE). UV-Vis-NIR spectroelectrochemical analyses were recorded by QE6500 and NIRQuest detectors (Ocean Optics), using ITO glass as a WE, Ag/AgCl (RE) and Pt coil (AE), comprised in a 2 mm cuvette with 0.25 mM emitters' solutions in BF₄ (0.1 M) and DCM. Solutions were submitted to five electrochemical cycles at 50 mVs⁻¹ scan rate, and UV-Vis-NIR spectra were recorded every 0.5 seconds in a potentiodynamic system. Potentiostatic EPR measurements were performed using JES-FA 200 (JEOL) spectrometer and a custom made cuvette containing 0.25 mM emitters' solutions with BF₄ (0.1 M) in DCM, 1 mm Pt wire (WE), Ag/AgCl

RESEARCH ARTICLE

(RE) and Pt coil (AE). EPR spectra were recorded stepwise (100 mV) *in situ* in a potentiostatic system.

Devices. HAT-CN (1,4,5,8,9,11-Hexaazatriphenylenehexacarbonitrile) was used as a Hole Injection Layer (HIL), NPB (*N,N'*-di(1-naphthyl)-*N,N'*-diphenyl-(1,1'-biphenyl)-4,4'-diamine) Hole Transport Layer (HTL), TPBi 2,2',2''-(1,3,5-Benzinetriyl)-tris(1-phenyl-1-*H*-benzimidazole) was introduced as an Electron Transport Layer (ETL). Lithium fluoride (LiF) and aluminium were used as the cathode. Organic semiconductors and aluminium were deposited at a rate of 1 Ås⁻¹, and the LiF layer was deposited at 0.1 Ås⁻¹. CBP 4,4'-bis(N-carbazolyl)-1,1'-biphenyl, were used as hosts for all emitters. All materials were purchased from Sigma Aldrich or Lumtec and were purified by temperature-gradient sublimation in a vacuum. OLEDs have been fabricated on pre-cleaned, patterned indium-tin-oxide (ITO) coated glass substrates with a sheet resistance of 20 Ω/sq and ITO thickness of 100 nm. All small molecules and cathode layers were thermally evaporated in a Kurt J. Lesker SuperSpectros 200 evaporation system under pressure of 10⁻⁷ mbar without breaking the vacuum. The sizes of pixels were 4 mm², 8 mm² and 16 mm². Each emitting layer has been formed by co-deposition of dopant and host at the specific rate to obtain 10% content of the emitter. The characteristics of the devices were recorded using a 6-inch integrating sphere (Labsphere) inside the glovebox connected to a Source Meter Unit and Ocean Optics USB4000 spectrometer.

Acknowledgements

Y.T. acknowledges a Grant-in-Aid for Scientific Research on Innovative Area "Aquatic Functional Materials: Creation of New Materials Science for Environment-Friendly and Active Functions" (JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number JP19H05716) from the MEXT (Ministry of Education, Culture, Science and Technology, Japan), a Grant-in-Aid for Scientific Research (B) (JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number JP20H02813), a Grant-in-Aid for Challenging Research (Exploratory) (JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number JP21K18960), and the Continuation Grants for Young Researchers from the Asahi Glass Foundation. Y.T. and S.M. acknowledge NIPPOH CHEMICALS for supplying *N,N*-diiodo-5,5-dimethylhydantoin (DIH). P.D. and P.Z.C. acknowledge the Polish National Science Centre funding, grant no. 2017/25/B/ST5/02488. P.D. and P.Z.C. acknowledge the supporting awards from the Rector of the Silesian University of Technology (04/040/BKM20/0124, 04/040/RGJ21/0149). Y.T., P.Z.C., and P.D. acknowledge the EU's Horizon 2020 for funding the OCTA project under grant agreement No 778158. Research work supported from the funds for science in 2018 - 2022 allocated to implementing an international co-financed project by the Polish Ministry of Education and Science. P.D. and P.Z.C. acknowledge the supporting actions from EU's Horizon 2020 ERA-Chair project ExCEED, grant agreement No 952008.

Keywords: dibenzophenazines • spectroelectrochemistry • electron paramagnetic resonance • electrochromism • TADF

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Entry for the Table of Contents

The change of donors in CT-based molecules significantly influences the charge carrier generation and follow-up reactions that affect the TADF emitter's stability. The TADF emitters can be easily electropolymerised, forming stable conjugated polymers. Electrochemically active TADF emitters possess significant electrochromic properties and can be used as both electrochromic and electroluminescence materials. The dual behaviour of the TADF emitters allows use in both OLED and Electrochromic Windows applications.